

NEW BISMALEIMIDE MATRIX RESIN-BISMALEIMIDE/
SUBSTITUTED BISMALEIMIDE COPOLYMER

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ABSTRACT

A new modified bismaleimide resin was synthesized by melting of two structurally different bismaleimides together. This resin, designated LL-45-2, was characterized by low melting point (about 55°C) and high decomposition temperature (>400°C). Properties of the resin, preparation and mechanical properties of the resin composite have been studied. The composites exhibits high strength retentivity at 250°C as well as good wet and heat stability.

INTRODUCTION

Bismaleimide (BMI) can form high crosslinking heat-resistant steric polymer by heat polymerization without formation of low molecular by-product, hence it is a potential matrix resin for heat-resistant composite. But BMI has a high melting point and is only soluble in non-protonic solvent of high boiling point. These bring many difficulties in preparing composites. Besides, polybismaleimide (PBMI) is brittle owing to its very high crosslinking degree. Recently, in order to solve these problems, many modified BMI resins of better performance and toughness have been developed (1), H.D. Stenzenberger et al. (2) mixed three structurally different BMI together by hot melting and obtained a resin Kerimid 353, which is of low melting point and can be used for preparing prepreps by hot melting.

In this paper we report a new modified BMI resin LL-45-2, which is obtained by hot melting two different BMI resin, one is a commercial product, 4,4'-bismaleimidodiphenylmethane (component A), the other is a substituted BMI (component B). LL-45-2 resin has a very low melting point (about 55°C) and is soluble in a solvent mixture with acetone as the main component. LL-45-2 copolymer is highly heat-resistant, its composite exhibits excellent mechanical property.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials

A. Components of LL-45 resin

Component A: 4, 4' -bismaleimidodiphenylmethane M.p. 155-160°C

Component B: BMI with substituted group, synthesized in our lab. M.p. 60-65°C, soluble in DMF, acetone and toluene.

B. LL-45 resin preparation

Powdered component A and component B with different molar ratios were mixed evenly, heated to 90-100°C till totally melted, cooled to room temperature and pulverized.

Table 1 LL-45 resin

No	1	2	3
A/B Molar ratio	2:1	1:1	1:2

2. Thermal properties of LL-45 resin

A. Differential Scanning Calorimetric analysis (DSC)

Melting and hot polymerization performance were measured by differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) CDR-1 at 10°C/min in nitrogen.

B. Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA)

Decomposition temperature of cured LL-45 resin was measured by a Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 in nitrogen at 10°C/min.

3. Preparation of composite

LL-45 resin was heated to 145-155°C and held for 20 minutes, then a solvent mixture (acetone: DMF=1:1) was dropped in refluxed for 20 minutes till the resin completely dissolved, cooled to room temperature. Carbon fiber (T-300) and E glass fiber were separately impregnated with this resin solution to make unidirectional prepregs, which were dried in vacuum (20mm Hg) at 80°C for 1-2 hour to remove the residual solvent.

The dried prepregs were stacked unidirectionally, heated to 160-165°C at 3°C/min. After 20 minutes, 1MPa pressure was added. Then it was heated to 210°C and held at this temperature for 4 hours. Afterwards it was cooled to room temperature. The laminate thus formed was taken out and cured in oven at 230-240°C for 10 hours.

4. Composite property measurements

Tensile properties was measured according to GB3354-82, flexural properties testing was measured according to GB3356-82, short beam shear strength was determined according to GB3375-82.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) was carried out by using a dynamic mechanical analyzer Dupont 9900.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Resin properties

A. Solubility

Component B, i.e. substituted BMI, owing to the steric hindrance effect of the substituted group, has less molecular stacking density and less crystallinity, hence better solubility. By experiment it can be dissolved organic solvents as acetone and toluene. If it is mixed with component A by hot-melting, the resin obtained should have a better solubility than resin made from pure component A. This was identified by experiments. Table 2 shows the experimental solubility data of LL-45-2 resin.

From table 2 it can be seen that, though LL-45-2 resin is soluble in acetone and toluene/acetone mixture, the homogeneous period (storage period without precipitate separation) is very short, hence, in face, it is not practicable. Solution can be stable for a long time, only when more polar solvent, acetone/DMF(1:1) mixture is used. Therefore, in prepregs this solvent should be used.

B. Curing reaction of resin

DSC curve of LL-45 resin and its components A, B are shown in Fig.1. The characteristic temperatures of DSC thermogram are shown in table 3. Owing to the presence of substituted group crystallinity of component B is poor, melting peak is not obvious and melting point is low, but the component A has a high melting point (160°C) and polymerizes immediately when melted. Component A and component B form eutectic mixture when mixed, melting point of which may be lower than that of any component.

Table 2 Solubility of LL-45-2 resin

Solvent Composition	Homogeneous Period
Acetone: DMF = 1:1	Long
Acetone: DMF = 2:1	6 days
Acetone: Toluene = 1:1	2 days
Acetone:	About 4 hours

Fig.1 DSC thermogram of LL-45 resin and components A,B

Table 3 Melting Point and Curing Temperatures of resin

A/B molar ratio	Melting Point (Perk value) ^o C	Curing Temperature ^o C		
		Peak Begin	Peak Maximum	Peak End
1:0	160	/	250	280
1:1	55	207	265	305
1:2	50	205	258	392
2:1	80	205	265	310
0:1	63	208	250	269

From figure 1 and table 3, it can be seen that, exothermic peaks of polymerization of resins all occur in a similar and broad temperature range. This shows that the substituted group in component B does not affect the polymerization activity apparently. Unlike component A, the melting points and curing temperatures of component B and A-B blend are far apart. This phenomena is especially profitable to the molding of its composites. Hence, performance of LL-45 resin is better.

From DSC data and on reference to curing parameters of other BMI resins, the curing parameters of LL-45 resin are so fixed. Curing is at 200^oC for 4 hours, aftertreatment is at 230^oC for 10 hours. The characteristic double bond absorption peaks of cured resin showed in infrared spectrum (690cm⁻¹, 3100cm⁻¹, 830cm⁻¹, 1640cm⁻¹) indicate that, the residual double bond absorption peaks in resin which is cured in the above condition, is very weak and does not vary with the increase of after treatment time.

C. Heat resistance of cured resin

Fig.2 shows the TGA and DTG curves of cured resin. Polymer decomposition temperature (PDT) and temperature of maximum decomposition rate (Tmax^D) obtained from the curve are listed in table 4. The decomposition temperature of LL-45 resin is over 400^oC, which is the typical decomposition

temperature of BMI resin. With the increase of component B in resin, PDT decreases slightly, this is concerned with the degree of polymer crosslinking (3). Component B, owing to the steric hindrance effect caused by the substituted group on polymerization, decrease the crosslinking density of polymer.

Fig.2 TGA and DIG curves of cured resin

Table 4 Thermal Decomposition Temperatures of LL-45 Resin

A/B Molar ratio	PDT °C	T ^D max °C
2:1	463	483
1:1	440	463
1:2	424	460

2. Composite properties

Properties of LL-45-2 resin composite are listed in table 5. As a reference, properties of composite Kerimid 353(4) are also listed. Owing to the property difference of fibers used in LL-45-2 and Kerimid 353, properties of the two composites can not be compared. Yet it can be seen that properties of LL-45-2 composite has reached an advanced level of modified BMI resin composite.

LL-45-2 composite exhibits good heat resistance. DMA measurement of glass fiber/LL-45-2 composite shows (Fig.3) its glass transition temperature T_g is 344°C, its modulus varies very little from temperature to 250°C, re-ventivity of its mechanical properties is over 60% (table 5). All these show the excellent heat resistance of LL-45-2 matrix resin.

Just as other BMI type resin composite, C/LL-45-2 composite exhibits higher wet and heat stability. Sample was dipped in boiling water for 100 hours, its water absorption (at equilibrium) was 1.4%, its short beam shear strength dropped from 91.6 MPa to 82.8 MPa, but its flexural strength only dropped from 2050 MPa to 1950 MPa.

CONCLUSION

BMI with substituted groups has much lower melting point and better solubility than BMI. LL-45 resin, obtained by melting of these two kinds of BMI together, has a low melting point, which is far below the polymerization temperature, and at the same time, maintains the heat resistance of PBMI, hence it is a heat resistant resin of better processing

property. Composite made from LL-45-2 has high mechanical strength, heat resistance and wet-heat stability, and is a hopeful matrix resin candidate for high temperature composite.

Table 5 Properties of Unidirectional Composites LL-45-2 and Kerimid 353

matrix fiber properties	LL-45-2		Kerimid 353	
	E-glass fiber	T-300 car- bon fiber	E-glass fiber	Modmor II (HS)
V _f %	67	66	60	60
Tensile strength (MPa)	—	1360	1060	1110
Tensile modulus (GPa)	—	155	41.8	172
Flexural strength (MPa)				
Room temperature	1710	2050	1213	1460
250°C	1120	1320	834	1158
Retentivity %	66	64	69	79
Flexural modulus (GPa)	—	137	42.1	165
Short-beam shear strength (MPa)				
Room temperature	96	91.6	75.8	75.8
250°C	56.3	69	49.6	49.6
Retentivity %	59	75	65	65
Glass transition temperature °C	344	—	—	—

Fig.3 DMA modulus curves of glass fiber/LL-45-2

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5. Metal Matrix Composites

